

New Value Perspective for Social Priceless Assets Through Digital Transformations

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Abstract

This paper endeavours to investigate the potential of digital transformation (DT) in enhancing the value of public assets with limited or no current management due to the scarcity of available information and the social nature of the asset. In certain regions, these assets experience high demand during peak hours, and the lack of effective management compels users to expend additional time and potentially contribute to increased pollution. Examples of the targeted assets include handicapped parking lots and reserved load/unload spaces in downtown areas. Despite experiencing significant usage pressure, leading to inefficiencies in last-mile logistics and increased pollution, municipalities have not implemented feedback mechanisms to improve their initial configurations. Typically, the initial setup lacks regular data collection on usage, requirements, and other relevant factors. This work proposes a smart monitoring system aimed at enhancing knowledge about usage patterns and requirements will not only facilitate the management of asset value creation but also provide crucial data for decision-making processes concerning the redefinition of these assets. Organizational implications, particularly in terms of change management, associated with such innovative solutions are also initially explored.

Keywords: Digital Transformation; Asset management; Management of priceless assets; LoraWAN; Blockchain 4.0

1. Introduction

This paper aims to explore the capacity of digital transformation (DT) to increase the value of public assets that currently lack management or have limited oversight, often due to insufficient available information and the communal aspect of the asset (Lafioune et al., 2023).

The rising prevalence of private car usage in urban regions, driven by rapid economic growth, outdated policies, and subsidies, stands as a primary factor contributing to the global concern of car parking in transportation and traffic management. The absence of effective management of downtown parking spaces in cities with high demand leads to inefficient utilization of parking areas and illegal vehicle parking. This situation causes wasted time and effort, exacerbating traffic congestion (Parmar et al., 2020).

A significant 35% loss in productive time was recorded due to the search for parking spots. Statistics from the USA indicate that this wasted time costs drivers approximately \$345 in fuel expenses. The requirements for parking, including for autonomous vehicles, must be carefully examined (Usharani & Karmel, 2022).

Hence, there is a requirement for adaptable smart services configurations to aid in the improved management of invaluable public assets. This paper will present a convenient setup encompassing both hardware and software to address this need effectively.

2. Literature review

Smart parking research has been conducted by different authors proposing alternative layers of technology (Usharani & Karmel, 2022), with different alternatives focused on cloud based solutions (Yun & Yuxin, 2010). Most of the contributions presents the generic concept of using cloud-based intelligent car parking services in smart cities as an important application of the Internet of Things (IoT) paradigm (Ji et al., 2014).

Many works have addressed the location at convenient places proposing solutions based on radar technology (Tiwari & Singh, 2016). It is ideal for outdoor detection over long distances, this solution becomes particularly relevant as European nations increasingly embrace electric shared cars to combat emission pollution. Given this trend, it becomes imperative to regulate recharging stations located around parking areas. To optimize their utilization, radar sensors are installed to deter unauthorized vehicles from occupying these spaces. Once a car parks in one of these spaces, the radar sensor can ascertain whether the vehicle has connected to the charger.

Other proposals include wireless ultrasonic sensor is powered by the wireless network to collect the information through high-frequency ultrasound waves (Jeon et al., 2014). However, a more integrative proposal is required, covering a variety of use cases, from street parking to handicap parking places, load/unload special areas, or even construction & demolition containers placed at the street, among others.

3. Methodology

The design principles adopted in this research were shaped by the contributions of (De Sordi, 2021; Gregório et al., 2021; Peffers et al., 2007; Venable et al., 2017). Their design approach encompasses a structured methodology involving problem identification, objective definition, solution development and evaluation, and ultimately, result communication. This method is

instrumental in guaranteeing that the resultant artifacts are effective, beneficial, and pertinent to the requirements of stakeholders within a given context. The context may include people, businesses, organizations, and existing technologies that are relevant to the problem. The Design science methodology also helps to identify any potential limitations or challenges that may need to be considered when developing an artifact.

There is a need for a more thorough conceptualization of wearable data within the complex semantic framework of industrial processes. This is especially crucial for understanding interactions between discrete equipment states and human operators, with the goal of reducing discrepancies in comprehending the entire process flow (Ordieres-Meré & Ortega-Mier, 2024).

Figure 1.- Adopted Framework, (source: Ordieres-Meré & Ortega-Mier, 2024)

4. Results

Using the public space to deploy and maintain smart devices create significant challenges, related to theft, vandalism, and other non-regular behaviours, and attending to the adopted framework and the use case capabilities, several data flows need to be integrated. On one side bay occupancy information, connected with geographic position. In addition, it is important to collect information related to vehicle user. To reconcile both data flows two different sensors need to be deployed in a way that no energy demands need to be fulfilled.

The next step is to create the logic behind the hardware deployment. Such logic requires that every user of a parking bay detected by Figure 2 (left) must self-register the bay usage Figure 2 (right). The same logic can be implemented for disabled parking places or for the control of construction waste containers placed at the street.

Figure 2.- Hardware components for the defined configuration. Left: magnetic sensor for vehicle presence placed at the center of the parking bay. Right: QR label to be placed at the sidewalk in parallel to the magnetic sensor.

The magnetic sensor placed in the robust case communicate changes (vehicle presence / absence) by means of LoraWAN technology (Aldahdouh et al., 2019; James & Nair, 2017). By means of these technology signals can reach around 1Km of distance to reach a gateway node usually placed at the outdoor lighting system, making it possible to send the information to the cloud (Siagian & Fernando, 2020). Parallel to the vehicle detection the user must self-register through the cellphone the presence, by scanning the QR, which includes the reference to the geographic position as well as the reference to its corresponding magnetic sensor.

When the user operates properly, s/he will indicate once the plate reference or the code provided by the municipal license in the case of waste containers temporary placed at the street. In this way not only finer control of the assets can be implemented without extra demand of human operators, but increased efficiency for police officers is reached when a vehicle is detected, and no registration happens in a time boundary of five minutes of each other.

Different rules can be automatically derived from the microservice oriented cloud platform, including usage of different type of parking bays, implementing different policies, per geographic sector. Implementation of fees, better tracking of municipal rules is also possible.

5. Discussion

The suggested solution not only enhances control over asset utilization but also offers an expanded knowledge base. This includes easily summarizing the average usage of parking bays throughout the day, on weekends, and so forth, on a per-street basis. Similarly, detailed information can be provided for disabled parking spots and areas with loading/unloading restrictions. Analyzing general bay usage yields insights into rotation, quantity, and average vacancy duration, facilitating ongoing policy enhancements. These improvements can be measured cost-effectively through key performance indicators (KPIs) derived from the new layer of information.

Furthermore, an aspect of even greater social significance is ensuring compliance with regulations governing disabled parking spots and designated load/unload times. This entails verifying that vehicles parked in disabled bays correspond to authorized license plates and users, and that the duration of loading operations aligns with permitted time frames. Additionally, the diversity of users can be readily assessed in aggregated terms.

6. Conclusions

This study presents a proposal for bolstering the monitoring of invaluable public assets, entailing moderate initial investment and minimal operational costs. Leveraging a high degree of integration as per the adopted framework, the system can generate high-quality, real-time information. This data can enhance the efficacy of punitive measures to enforce established regulations and facilitate the adaptive re-planning of specific locations based on observed usage patterns.

The current level of information collected by municipalities does not support the kind of strategic planning facilitated by regular monitoring of key performance indicators (KPIs). However, with a moderate investment, which includes the installation of sensors and light gateways on-site, as well as QR codes on sidewalks for physical hardware, and the implementation of a microservice system to process the generated data, a powerful yet cost-effective information system can be established. Given the manageable additional effort for management, anticipated changes can be minimized, thus reducing resistance to change. Nevertheless, there will be a need to reallocate resources and acquire new skills to effectively utilize the gathered information.

The system's management presents challenges as it necessitates reallocating additional IT services. Besides the demands of change management, there's a need to furnish users with additional information to counterbalance the potential negative perception of a swift and efficient punitive system. Hence, efforts should focus on not only societal education but also enhancing the perceived value for individuals, thereby addressing both aspects effectively.

Additional research is necessary to develop comprehensive solutions that address both technical and managerial aspects cohesively. This holistic approach is essential to ensure effectiveness and efficiency across all dimensions of the system.

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